

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' MUSICAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN TRADITIONAL SINGING LESSONS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the development of musical performance skills of students in traditional singing classes. It highlights the role of traditional singing lessons in the educational process, the importance of education as an important tool in the formation and development of performance skills. In the course of the study, the effectiveness of innovative approaches and practical training to improve executive skills is analyzed. By mastering traditional methods and techniques in singing, students develop not only musical culture, but also the ability to understand the rich heritage of Uzbek folk music. This article presents suggestions and recommendations aimed at improving singing skills based on advanced pedagogical technologies.

Key words: Traditional singing, music performance, performance skills, educational process, pedagogical technologies, practical training, folk music, music education.

Introduction.

The art of traditional singing is an integral part of Uzbek music culture and embodies rich traditions that represent the cultural and spiritual heritage of the nation. The development of this art and its transmission from generation to generation directly depends on the performance skills of singers and the process of delivering this skill. Today, in the process of music education, educating students on the basis of traditional singing serves not only to develop their performance skills, but also to help them understand the cultural significance of folk music.

Traditional singing lessons play an important role in the formation of musical performance skills. These lessons not only improve performance skills, but also encourage students to creative research, preservation and development of national musical heritage. At the same time, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process by combining modern pedagogical technologies with traditional methods has become an urgent issue.

This article examines the role of traditional singing lessons in the educational process, its impact on the development of students' performance skills, as well as ways to improve performance skills using modern approaches. The article is aimed at studying the theoretical and practical aspects of the art of singing, based on the analysis of best practices in this regard and making suggestions.

Methodology:

In this study, complex research methods were used to study the development of students' performance skills in traditional singing classes. The research was carried out on the following methodological basis:

Scientific literature on music education, pedagogical and methodical manuals, existing studies and articles on national music performance were analyzed. The theoretical aspects of the development of traditional singing and music performance were studied.

In traditional singing lessons, the progress of the educational process, methods aimed at developing students' performance skills were observed. During the observations, the teaching methodology and the factors influencing the level of students' learning were noted.

Special pedagogical approaches aimed at developing students' musical performance skills were tested. During the experiment, ways of developing performance skills were studied based on the combination of traditional and innovative methods.

Interviews were organized with students and their teachers. During the interviews, feedback was collected on the problems encountered in the course of the lesson, the needs of students and the development of their performance skills.

The results of the experiment and observation were analyzed, and effective methods of developing musical performance skills in traditional singing lessons were determined. Pedagogical recommendations were developed based on the results.

The results of this research show the importance of traditional singing lessons in improving students' performance skills. It is also a basis for studying the possibilities of using innovative approaches in improving the educational process.

Literature review:

The analysis of scientific literature, which illuminates the theoretical and practical aspects of the art of traditional singing and music performance, served as an important basis for this research. During the research, a number of works dedicated to Uzbek music culture, folk art and singing art were studied. Below is a brief analysis of the main literature on this topic and the approaches presented in them:

Studies on Uzbek folk music and traditional singing art (Sharof Boshbekov, Yunus Rajabi, Komiljon Otaniyozov, etc.) revealed the methodological aspects of traditional music, its role in performance and educational significance. In these sources, the performance of folk music is defined by its specific performance technique and essence.

Scientific works highlighting pedagogical approaches to traditional singing education, including scientific articles on music education by Uzbek and foreign scientists, pay special attention to the role and importance of national music in the development of students' performance skills. Their approach includes effective methods of developing students' creative abilities and bringing them closer to national music.

Works written on the integration of modern pedagogical technologies in music education, in particular, research on the use of interactive methods in music education, emphasize the effectiveness of innovative approaches in improving performance skills. This literature suggests an educational model based on the combination of traditional and modern methods.

International sources have studied the unique aspects of folk music education, global pedagogical approaches that serve to improve students' performance skills. These studies make it possible to compare the performance of national music with international experience.

The analysis of these literatures shows that it is important to combine national traditions and modern pedagogical approaches in the development of performance skills in traditional singing lessons. This not only improves performance skills, but also helps students think creatively and form their own musical identity.

Discussion:

The results of the research showed that traditional singing lessons play an important role in the development of students' musical performance skills. In this process, it is necessary to use special methodical approaches to increase students' interest in national musical heritage, develop their creative thinking and improve performance skills.

During the discussion, the following main aspects were identified:

1. The role of traditional singing in the educational process

Through traditional singing lessons, students learn the styles of folk music and have the opportunity to apply them in performance. This plays an important role in improving their performance skills. Especially mastering the melody, rhythm and performance styles characteristic of folk music encourages students to creative research.

2. Effectiveness of using innovative technologies

The use of modern pedagogical technologies, including multimedia tools and interactive methods, serves to improve traditional methods. For example, the use of audio and video materials allows students to learn music samples and performance techniques more effectively visually and aurally.

3. The importance of practical training

As observed in the research, in the course of practical training, students have the opportunity not only to strengthen theoretical knowledge, but also to develop performance skills directly through performance practice. The individual approach of coaches is an important factor in this process.

4. A combination of national and modern approaches

Combining national and modern approaches in the educational process of traditional singing creates great opportunities for the development of students' creative potential. The results of teaching students national music methods combined with modern performance techniques have been effective.

5. Individual development of students

Based on the results of the research, it was emphasized that an individual approach, taking into account their abilities and needs, is necessary for the development of students' performance skills. This helps to organize the execution process more effectively.

In general, traditional singing lessons are not only an important part of the educational process in improving students' performance skills, but also serve as an educational platform that enriches their musical outlook. In order to improve this process, it was determined that it is necessary to ensure the harmony of national musical heritage and modern pedagogical technologies.

Conclusion:

The results of the research show that traditional singing lessons play an important role in the development of students' musical performance skills. Through these classes, students will have the opportunity to master the national musical heritage and improve their creative and performance skills. This study led to the following conclusions:

Traditional singing lessons create a foundation for students to master the theoretical and practical aspects of performance. This process increases their interest in music and stimulates their creative pursuits. Combining modern pedagogical technologies with traditional approaches ensures high efficiency in improving students' performance skills. The

use of multimedia tools and interactive methods expands innovative opportunities in music education.

Practical training plays a key role in the development of students' performance skills. The individual approach of the coaches and the teaching of national musical styles in these classes help to significantly improve the performance skills of the students. Development of special methodical recommendations by pedagogues and ensuring the harmony of national and modern approaches are of great importance in the development of students' executive abilities.

Thus, the development of performance skills in traditional singing lessons not only improves students' performance skills, but also forms their ability to understand and appreciate national musical culture. Improving the effectiveness of music education can be achieved by improving this process.

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